

Post-Disaster Psychosocial Support Action Plan for University Staff and Family: Results of Pilot Needs Assessment Application

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Purpose

On February 6, 2023, earthquakes of magnitude 7.8 and 7.6 struck Turkey, causing damage in 11 provinces and major destruction in four of them. Official estimates are that at least 56,000 people died and at least 2.5 million were displaced. One of the hardest-hit provinces is a city of more than 800,000 people that is home to two state universities. Like all the people living in this city, university employees have suffered greatly from this devastation. Some of these people have lost their relatives, others have lost their homes, and most of them are suffering from various psychological problems. Disasters can have a traumatic effect on people who experience or witness them. Psychological problems such as acute or post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety, and depression can be observed in individuals who experience disasters (Horovitz et al., 1991; Gokalp, 2002; Madianos & Evi, 2010). As an institution, universities represent the face of a city toward development and innovation. For academics, who already face various problems related to their well-being due to their profession (Henny et al., 2014; Sverdlik & Hall, 2020), it is important to urgently address the negative psychological effects of the earthquake disaster. Therefore, in a university with approximately 6000 employees affected by the earthquake disaster, an action plan for psychosocial support measures was created, and actions in line with this plan were started. The first step was to identify the current situation and

needs. This study aims to share the results of the pilot implementation of the needs assessment step.

Design

Academics of the faculty of education were determined as the sample for the pilot application and a survey was used for this descriptive step. The survey consisted of three sections: demographic information, general health questionnaire, and support needs. Demographic information included gender, age, job title, and current place of residence. The General Health Questionnaire (GHQ), a psychometric screening instrument to identify prevalent psychological conditions, consists of 28 items and four sub-dimensions with 7 items each. These dimensions are: Somatic Symptoms, Anxiety and Insomnia, Social Dysfunction, and Severe Depression. The items of the scale were scored on a 0-3 scale in accordance with the proposal of Goldberg et al. (1998). The total scale score is 84. Goldberg et al. (1998) suggest that respondents with a total score of 23 or less should be classified as nonpsychiatric, whereas participants with a score of 24 or more may be classified as psychiatric; however, this score is not an exact cutoff. It is suggested that researchers establish a cutoff value in accordance with the sample mean. Prior to implementation, the psychosocial support team leader, a dynamically oriented brief intensive emergency psychotherapy specialist and counselor trainer, presented the intervention action plan to faculty in an online session lasting approximately one hour (75 people participated) and asked for volunteers to complete the questionnaire (63 people).

Results

Of those who completed the questionnaire, 56 were academics (30 women, 26 men) and the data from the academics are presented in this study. The age range of the participants was 25-64 years ($M = 44.23$, $SD = 11.62$) and their distribution by academic title is shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Academic titles of the participants

The participants' places of residence are shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2. Current places of residence of participants

On the other hand, according to the GHQ data, the average total score of participants was 46.30 (SD= 2.33) for women and 36.65 (SD= 3.09) for men. For the Somatic Symptoms subscale, participants' mean total scores were 11.50 (SD= .71) for women and 7.89 (SD= .75) for men. For the Anxiety and Insomnia subscale, participants' mean total scores were 15.37 (SD= .91) for females and 11.04 (SD= 1.09) for males. For the Social Dysfunction subscale, participants' mean total scores were 13.23 (SD= .67) for women and 12.39 (SD= .84) for men. For the Severe Depression subscale, participants' mean total scores were 6.20 (SD= .67) for women and 5.35

(SD= .81) for men. Independent-samples t-tests were conducted to examine gender differences. The results showed that there were significant differences between men and women in somatic symptoms ($t(54) = -3.51, p < .001$) and anxiety and insomnia ($t(54) = -3.09, p = .003$). There was also a significant difference between males and females in mean total GHQ scores ($t(54) = -2.53, p = .014$). According to these results, female participants exhibited more somatic symptoms, experienced more anxiety and insomnia, and were generally more psychologically distressed than male participants. Three participants responded "I have thought about suicide" to the item aimed at understanding suicidal thoughts among the items of the GHQ. Two of these participants were male and one was female. Only the female participant shared her information and indicated that she wanted to seek psychological support. Apart from this female participant, four other participants indicated that they needed psychological support for themselves and two participants indicated that they needed psychological support for their family members. In addition, 22 of the participants indicated their urgent needs, and it was found that the most frequently requested need was a safe place to live. In accordance with these data, it was found that the participants' psychological health was significantly affected by the earthquake disaster. All individuals who requested psychological support were referred to professional psychological counselors. Consistent with the anamnestic work, it is assumed that these individuals will be referred to appropriate medical assistance or enrolled in individual/group psychological counseling or psychoeducation programs. The latest status of studies on these individuals will be presented at the congress to be held in June.

Implications

Although the earthquake disaster that is the reason for this study was experienced locally, the whole world is threatened by natural or man-made disasters, as the Covid 19 pandemic has shown as a recent example. Any study of such situations, including this study, which is based on (unfortunately) real examples, has the potential to provide clues for mitigating potential disaster situations.

Resources

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